

Digital Essay Competition

2025 Annual Report

15,221 Total Essays	312 Schools	35 Counties	452 Learners with Disabilities
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Prepared for the Kenya Ministry of Education

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Executive Summary

In 2025, eKitabu implemented the **13th annual Digital Essay Competition (DEC)** in alignment with its mission to advance inclusive and equitable quality education for all. The Competition invited students from over 6,000 public and private schools across Kenya, emphasising the importance of amplifying learners' voices and providing a platform for young writers to express their ideas, perspectives, and creativity.

The 2025 competition ran from May to October and targeted upper primary, junior, and secondary school students across multiple categories: English, Kiswahili, Art, Kenyan Sign Language (KSL), Braille, French, German, Arabic, and Mandarin, with Mandarin introduced as a new category in 2025.

15,221 Total Entries	312 Participating Schools	35 Counties Reached	112,522 Cumulative Essays Since 2013
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Key Changes in 2025

1. Integration of a research component to generate learner-centred evidence linked to the annual competition theme.
2. Highest-ever participation of learners with disabilities, 452 students from 43 schools, widening the Competition's commitment to inclusive education.
3. Introduction of Mandarin as a competition category, expanding opportunities for multilingual expression and global language learning.
4. Addition of a Poetry category (*Chapa Shairi*) to broaden creative expression beyond conventional essay writing.
5. Implementation of online second-round judging, improving efficiency, consistency, and turnaround time in evaluation.
6. Use of a single essay question focused on fostering a love of reading, applied across all levels of the competition.

This report summarises the process, results, research insights, and lessons learned from the 2025 Digital Essay Competition. eKitabu extends its sincere appreciation to the Ministry of Education for its continued support and looks forward to continued collaboration in 2026.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Full Form
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CBE	Competency-Based Education
DEC	Digital Essay Competition
DSNE	Directorate of Special Needs Education
FEDWEN	Federation of Deaf Women Empowerment Network
KEPSHA	Kenya Primary School Heads Association
KESSHA	Kenya Secondary School Heads Association
KIB	Kenya Institute for the Blind
KICD	Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development
KISE	Kenya Institute of Special Education
KPA	Kenya Publishers Association
KPSA	Kenya Private Schools Association
KSL	Kenyan Sign Language
MoE	Ministry of Education
NIBF	Nairobi International Book Fair
OPD	Organisation of Persons with Disabilities
RKO	Regional Kick-Off

Introduction

The 2025 Digital Essay Competition (DEC) marked the 13th annual implementation of eKitabu's flagship initiative dedicated to advancing inclusive and equitable quality education across Kenya. In alignment with its core mission, the competition provided a national platform for over 6,000 public and private schools to amplify learners' voices, fostering an environment where young writers could express their original ideas, perspectives, and creativity.

The 2025 cycle, which ran from May to October, targeted students in upper primary, junior, and secondary school levels. To ensure broad accessibility, the programme utilised a multi-channel submission approach, allowing students to submit entries through an online portal (essay.ekitabu.com) as well as alternative channels suited to diverse contexts nationwide.

A defining feature of this year's competition was its expansion into multilingual and creative categories. Beyond the traditional English and Kiswahili streams, students participated in Art, Kenyan Sign Language (KSL), Braille, French, German, and Arabic. Notably, 2025 saw the introduction of Mandarin as a new language category and *Chapa Shairi* for poetry, broadening the scope for global language learning and creative expression.

Figure 1: Map representation of the DEC participants

Furthermore, the 2025 DEC achieved a significant programmatic milestone by integrating a structured research component focused on the theme “What is your favourite book and why?” This initiative generated learner-centred evidence on reading motivations and access to materials, directly aligning the competition with the goals of Kenya’s Competency-Based Education (CBE). By combining large-scale participation, including the highest-ever turnout of learners with disabilities, with rigorous evaluation and research, the 2025 Digital Essay

Competition continues to serve as a vital tool for developing critical thinking and innovative minds among Kenyan youth.

Primary Benefits of the Digital Essay Competition

1. Encourages all students, including learners with special needs and disabilities, to write, develop, and express their original ideas and perspectives.
2. Enhances creativity and critical thinking among students and teachers.
3. Supports learning through the enhancement of writing skills.
4. Uses learner-generated content to inform evidence-based education practice through research.

DEC 2025 Goals

1. Expand national reach and participation by engaging the highest possible number of students and schools across Kenya.
2. Reach and recognise winning students from special needs schools to widen inclusivity.
3. Promote originality, ethical writing, and responsible use of AI in essay writing while strengthening awareness of academic integrity and digital ethics.
4. Encourage young writers by providing them with a platform to express their thoughts creatively, in multiple languages and formats.
5. Reach and recognise winning students from schools in the main refugee camps in Kenya: Dadaab and Kakuma.
6. Strengthen collaboration with teachers, schools, and partners to support learner participation and quality submissions.
7. Generate more online entries across all categories, including English, Kiswahili, French, German, Art, KSL, Braille, Arabic, and Mandarin.

Key Events

The 2025 Digital Essay Competition was anchored by four distinct event types designed to ensure national reach, deep school engagement, and sustained visibility throughout the competition cycle.

Official Launch

The Official Launch is a high-profile annual event held at one or two strategically selected schools, typically pairing one primary and one secondary institution in different regions to ensure broad national reach. These events formally introduce and reintroduce the competition to students and teachers across the country, serving as a gathering point for Ministry of Education officials, education stakeholders, partners, and the broader eKitabu community. A central highlight of each launch is the unveiling of the DEC questions for primary, junior, and senior school categories. Beyond revealing the competition topics, the event provides a comprehensive overview of the programme's strategic goals, celebrates the success of the alumni community, and outlines the implementation timelines and operational plans for the current year.

Mini Launch

The Mini Launch is a localised version of the Official Launch, held at a specific school within a selected region. It allows students and teachers from neighbouring schools to participate and creates momentum at the regional level in support of the national rollout.

Regional Kick-Off (RKO)

Regional Kick-Offs are a series of school-level events that engage students and educators across selected regions. RKOs are used to introduce DEC to new schools and to conduct follow-up activities in existing ones. By recognising winners, finalists, and teachers on-site, these events effectively encourage learners and entire school communities to join or remain active within the DEC network.

School Visits

School visits are targeted engagements by the eKitabu team, especially to new DEC schools, with the objective of personally engaging head teachers and teachers and securing their commitment to mobilise student participation.

Organisation of the Competition

The systematic organisation of the 2025 Digital Essay Competition began with securing formal approval and authority from the Ministry of Education. Operational success relied on a robust, multi-tier partnership ecosystem. Strategic collaboration with the Directorate of Special Needs Education (DSNE) was instrumental in advancing inclusive and equitable education, facilitating specialised outreach to learners with disabilities across the country.

At the regional level, partnerships with regional ministry offices, head teachers, and a dedicated network of eKitabu DEC agents provided the necessary infrastructure to reach diverse and remote school populations.

Key Implementation Activities

- Strategic Launch Events: Two high-profile Official Launch events, one primary and one secondary, complemented by seven Regional Kick-Off (RKO) events covering 27 counties.
- Targeted Outreach: Direct school visits conducted across Nairobi, Machakos, Kiambu, and Kajiado counties.
- Multi-Channel Communication: Distribution of digital posters to teachers, agents, and parents through WhatsApp and online channels.
- Real-time Engagement: Social media updates and bulk SMS notifications at every stage of the competition cycle.

Summary of Events 2025

Event	Schools Reached	Counties Covered
Official Launch - Primary (State House Primary School)	17	Nairobi
Official Launch - Secondary (Kapsabet High School)	54	Nandi, Uasin Gishu, Kericho, Vihiga, Kakamega, Bungoma, Trans Nzoia
1st Regional Kick-Off	4	Garissa, Wajir
2nd Regional Kick-Off	17	Nakuru, Kericho, Kisumu, Siaya, Busia
3rd Regional Kick-Off	6	Homa Bay, Migori
4th Regional Kick-Off	11	Uasin Gishu, Trans Nzoia, Kakamega, Bungoma
5th Regional Kick-Off	9	Muranga, Nyeri, Kirinyaga, Meru, Embu, Isiolo
6th Regional Kick-Off	12	Mombasa, Tana River

Event	Schools Reached	Counties Covered
7th Regional Kick-Off	10	Uasin Gishu, Baringo
School Visits	29	Kiambu, Nairobi, Machakos, Kajiado
TOTAL	169	27 Counties

Sponsors and Partners

The 2025 Digital Essay Competition was made possible through the generous support of sponsors and the collaboration of strategic partners whose commitment to education and literacy helped sustain the programme's national reach and inclusive focus.

2025 Sponsors and Partners

Organisation	Role
Ubongo International	Programme sponsor and education content partner
Kenya Publishers Association (KPA)	Publishing sector partner supporting essay evaluation and prizes
Kenya Primary School Heads Association (KEPSHA)	Primary-school mobilisation and engagement partner
Kenya Secondary School Heads Association (KESSHA)	Secondary-school mobilisation and engagement partner
Kenya Private Schools Association (KPSA)	Private-school engagement partner
Ministry of Education — Directorate of Special Needs Education (DSNE)	Strategic partner for inclusive outreach
Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB)	Specialist judging partner for Braille submissions
Kenya Institute of Special Education (KISE)	Specialist partner for KSL video evaluation

Our DEC 2025 Teachers

As observed since DEC's inception in 2013, teachers play a pivotal role in the programme's success. In 2025, eKitabu worked with over 420 teachers drawn from diverse roles and institutions. Without teachers, the competition's national reach and quality of submissions would not be possible.

Categories of Teachers Engaged

- School head teachers.
- Language teachers of English, Kiswahili, French, German, Arabic, and Mandarin from both mainstream and special needs schools.
- Senior teachers and ICT champions, including Computer Studies teachers.
- eKitabu DEC field agents who are also teachers.
- Contact teachers in schools serving the refugee camps.
- DEC judges.

eKitabu engaged teachers through industry events, school visits, social media platforms, and frequent phone calls. Teachers in the Nairobi metropolis were further supported through direct school visits. In 2025, eKitabu placed particular emphasis on recognising teachers' contributions through awards and certification. Teachers valued receiving qualitative feedback from judges' comments on their students' essays and on schools' overall performance.

Teacher Participation (2013–2025)

Year	New Teachers	% New	Return Teachers	Total Teachers
2013	76	100%	N/A	76
2014	130	66%	67	197
2015	35	36%	62	97
2016	181	78%	49	230
2017	216	84%	39	255
2018	218	51%	202	420
2019	295	61%	185	480
2020	39	27%	106	145
2021	69	30%	159	228
2022	72	28%	180	252
2023	211	60%	142	353
2024	344	80%	87	431

Year	New Teachers	% New	Return Teachers	Total Teachers
2025	310	73%	110	420

Key Observation

Since 2013, eKitabu has consistently built partnerships with teachers from diverse schools, recognising their critical role in mobilising student participation. In 2025, 73% of engaged teachers were new to the programme, a strong indicator of continued national expansion.

Plans for Teachers in DEC 2026

- Engage teachers from diverse schools from the outset, beginning with the development of the competition theme.
- Collaborate closely with teachers to ensure complete and accurate data during learner registration and submission.
- Involve teachers more actively in guiding students on originality, ethical writing, and constructive use of AI.
- Expand teacher participation by engaging more educators from partner organisations.
- Strengthen the involvement of teachers and agents in regional event planning and execution.
- Formally recognise and appreciate all teachers who supported the programme in 2025.
- Work closely with contact teachers in refugee camps to improve registration and increase participation.
- Increase participation from Nairobi County schools by applying lessons learned from the 2025 competition.

Process and Analysis

The 2025 DEC process was well-planned in advance and rigorously executed. The few adjustments made during the cycle related mainly to scheduling; for example, the closing deadline was extended by two weeks to allow for additional submissions. The competition proceeded through three clearly defined stages: Discovery, Participation, and Judging.

Stage I: Discovery & Awareness

eKitabu created awareness of the Competition through multiple channels to ensure maximum reach across Kenya:

- Bulk SMS to schools in the DEC network, including launch announcements, topic communications, registration instructions, deadline reminders, prize details, and prize-giving information.
- WhatsApp Groups for teachers, head teachers, parents, and special needs school communities.
- Digital posters distributed to agents, teachers, and parents, mostly through WhatsApp and online channels.
- Consistent social media updates across major platforms, serving as reminders and calls to action for growing follower communities.
- Presence at industry events (KESSHA, KEP SHA, KPSA, Book Fairs) to grow school contacts.

Stage II: Participation

Entrants were encouraged to submit essays through the online platform at essay.ekitabu.com. The registration and submission process was kept simple to minimise barriers to online submission.

Registration

Students registered by creating an account with their personal and school details. The system issued unique user IDs upon completion of registration.

Essay Submission

The platform supported typed or pasted essays, Word documents, PDFs, scanned handwritten essays, and art submissions. Special needs learners could submit essays in Braille, audio recordings, or sign language videos. WhatsApp submissions were also maintained as a channel, and physical copies could be delivered to eKitabu's offices in person, through courier services, or through field agents in the regions.

Stage III: Judging

The Competition employed a two-round judging process to ensure rigour, consistency, and quality of evaluation. In 2025, an important innovation was the introduction of online second-

round judging, which significantly improved turnaround time while maintaining evaluation standards. The judging process is described in detail in the following section.

Judging Process

First-Round Judging

A panel of highly experienced teachers, many serving as national examiners, reviewed all submissions and grouped them into two categories: Upper Primary and Junior School (Grades 5-9) and Secondary School (Forms 2-4). Essays scoring in the top tier were designated as Finalist Essays and advanced to the second round. Specialist judges were engaged for French, German, Arabic, Mandarin, KSL, and Braille categories.

In advance of the Competition, the judges sat together as a team to review and validate the marking criteria. For each category, at least the top 20 essays were selected to proceed to the second-round judging. For specialist categories, a smaller but similarly rigorous shortlist was prepared.

Second-Round Judging

A distinguished panel of professionals from Kenyan publishing firms, school heads, heads of language departments, and university professors reviewed Finalist Essays to select final winners. In 2025, this round was conducted entirely online, improving efficiency without compromising quality.

Judging of Special Needs Students' Essays

Since the majority of essays in this category were Braille and KSL videos, eKitabu engaged judges from the Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB) for Braille essays and the Kenya Institute of Special Education (KISE), together with teachers from schools of deaf learners who have KSL skills for sign language videos.

Judging Criteria

Each essay was required to reflect the contestant's own research, writing, and original thinking. Any essay the judges deemed to have been written by someone else was disqualified. Judging weighed a balance of regional, gender, and social factors but prioritised overall essay quality according to the five criteria below.

Criterion	Description	Max Score
I. Comprehension	How well the essay reflects thorough comprehension of the question; essays may be approached as narrative, dialogue, or conventional essay form	20
II. Organisation	Logical and coherent progression; corroborating evidence supports the main argument	20
III. Conclusions	Whether conclusions follow logically from the argument and how compelling they are	20
IV. Creativity	Portrayal of an innovative or creative angle on the	20

Criterion	Description	Max Score
	question	
V. Writing	Correct grammar, spelling, and punctuation; concise language	20
TOTAL		100

Grading Bands

80–100: A | 70–79: B | 60–69: C | 50–59: D | Below 50: Fail

First-Round Judges 2025

eKitabu thanks the following judges, drawn from top-performing schools, publishing partners, and specialist institutions, for their dedication to the 2025 Competition.

English Category

#	Name	School	Level
1.	Kennedy Mbuvi	Kitulu Secondary School	Secondary
2.	Immaculate Auma Wambura	Maranda High School	Secondary
3.	Robert Wandera Nyabola	Chenjeni Primary School	Primary
4.	Ruth Nyaga	Olympic Primary School	Primary
5.	Damaris Sayo	Bar Odar Special School	Special
6.	Julia Owuato Okeyo Ojiambo	Chepkoilel Primary School	Primary
7.	Reagan Okoth	Migingo Girls High School	Secondary
8.	Shem Kodonde	Kangemi Primary School	Primary
9.	Mercy W. Mugo	State House Primary School	Primary

Kiswahili Category

#	Name	School	Level
1.	Beatrice Kagai Kikuyu	St. Monica Primary School	Primary
2.	Peris Wambulwa	Karapul Primary School	Primary
3.	Moses Kituyi Moreka	Alliance Girls High School	Secondary
4.	Peter Odongo	Kakamega Primary School	Primary

#	Name	School	Level
5.	Brenda Ambula	Ndurarwa Primary School	Primary
6.	Amos Kipsang	Emining Boys High School	Secondary
7.	Franklin Mukembu	Munithu Mixed Day Secondary School	Secondary

Kenyan Sign Language (KSL) Videos

#	Name	School/Institution	Level
1.	Monica Muthoni	Tumutumumu School for the Deaf	Special
2.	Evans Burichani	Kenya National Association of the Deaf	OPD
3.	Aska Josephine	FEDWEN	OPD
4.	Damaris Wanjiku	Murang'a School for the Hearing Impaired	Special
5.	Modest Oswago	Murang'a Secondary School for the Deaf	Special
6.	Bernard Ragwel	St. Kizito Girls Secondary School for the Deaf	Special

Braille Category

#	Name	School/Institution	Level
1.	Martin Obiero	Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB)	OPD
2.	Phenny Akoth Onyango	Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB)	OPD
3.	Lydia Kyalo Karanja	Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB)	OPD
4.	Mercy Manyala	Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB)	OPD

French Category

#	Name	School	Level
1.	Celine Okumu	Bishop Gatimu Ngandu Girls	Secondary
2.	Diana Naliaka Wanyonyi	Jamhuri High School	Secondary
3.	Jameson Mativo	Kaumoni Boys High School	Secondary

Name	School/Institution	Level
German Category		
Jackline Atieno Okumu	Uasin Gishu High School	Secondary
Arabic Category		

Name	School/Institution	Level
Amina Atitala Suleiman	Mahada Girl Training Institute	Tertiary
	Mandarin	
Susan	Kenyatta University Confucius Centre	Tertiary

DEC 2025: Participation and Final Results

The 2025 Digital Essay Competition received 15,221 entries across all categories, representing students from 312 schools in 35 counties. The competition also recorded the highest-ever participation of learners with disabilities in its history.

15,221 Total Entries	312 Schools (211 Primary, 101 Sec.)	35 Counties	43 Special Needs Schools
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Entries by Category

Category	Number of Entries
English	9,576
Kiswahili	3,715
Art	722
Braille	236
Arabic	85
Chapa Shairi (Poetry)	85
KSL (Kenyan Sign Language)	78
French	76
German	45
Mandarin (new in 2025)	5
Special Needs (across categories)	452
Kakuma Refugee Camp	67

Figure 2: Distribution of 2025 entries across categories. English and Kiswahili together account for the majority of submissions.

Historical Participation -Total Entries (2013 to 2025)

Year	Primary	Secondary	Total	Cumulative
2013	381	337	718	718
2014	1,397	665	2,062	2,780
2015	1,366	754	2,120	4,900
2016	4,876	2,226	7,102	12,002
2017	3,719	1,586	5,305	17,307
2018	10,438	2,626	13,064	30,371
2019	9,826	3,739	13,565	43,936
2020	763	1,123	1,886	45,822
2021	9,782	3,694	13,476	59,298
2022	9,939	3,088	10,327	69,327
2023	5,984	3,628	9,612	78,939
2024	14,755	3,607	18,362	97,301
2025	13,283	1,829	15,221	112,522

Key Observation

Primary school entries consistently dominate the competition. In 2025, 87% of all essays came from primary and junior school students. The cumulative total has now surpassed 112,500 essays since 2013.

Total Entries per Year (2013-2025)

Figure 3: Total essay submissions 2013-2025. Note the steep growth to a 2024 peak of 18,362, the COVID-related dip in 2020, and the sustained high participation in 2025.

Entries by Gender (2013 to 2025)

Year	Male	Female	Total
2013	314	378	692
2014	969	1,093	2,062
2015	968	1,152	2,120
2016	3,665	3,437	7,102
2017	2,410	2,895	5,305
2018	5,849	7,215	13,064
2019	6,319	7,246	13,565
2020	829	1,057	1,886
2021	5,373	8,103	13,476

Year	Male	Female	Total
2022	4,629	5,629	10,258
2023	3,812	5,527	9,339
2024	7,466	10,710	18,176
2025	6,172	9,049	15,221

Key Observation

Since 2013, female students have consistently submitted more essays than male students. In 2025, girls accounted for 59% of all entries, consistent with patterns observed in 2023 and 2024.

Figure 4: Entries by gender 2013-2025. Female students have consistently submitted more essays than male students across every year of the competition.

Entries by Main Categories - English & Kiswahili (2015 to 2025)

Year	English	Kiswahili	Total
2015	1,690	430	2,120
2016	4,939	2,163	7,102
2017	3,748	1,557	5,305
2018	7,948	5,054	13,002

Year	English	Kiswahili	Total
2019	7,931	5,456	13,387
2020	979	844	1,823
2021	7,741	5,160	12,901
2022	6,349	3,554	9,903
2023	4,510	4,011	8,521
2024	11,691	4,233	15,924
2025	9,576	3,715	13,291

Key Observation

Since 2015, the number of English essays compared with Kiswahili essays has always been higher by at least 25%. In 2025, English essays were 63% of the total.

Other Categories Since 2019

Category	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Art	20	26	158	96	129	1,515	722
KSL	7	6	23	62	45	50	78
Braille	86	23	53	98	32	117	236
French	56	17	68	55	52	103	76
German	11	5	12	16	36	29	45
Arabic	0	0	28	15	29	93	85
Mandarin	—	—	—	—	—	—	5
Chapa Shairi	—	—	—	—	—	—	85

Key Observation

2025 registered the highest number of Braille submissions (236) in DEC history, and the introduction of Mandarin and Chapa Shairi broadened the range of creative and linguistic expression in the competition.

School Participation by Category (2013 to 2025)

Year	Primary	Secondary	Total
2013	31	54	85
2014	95	176	271
2015	60	112	172
2016	143	118	261
2017	108	69	177
2018	241	115	356
2019	210	155	365
2020	243	188	431
2021	158	82	240
2022	158	139	297
2023	139	117	256
2024	256	184	440
2025	211	101	312

Key Observation

For over a decade, the number of registered primary schools has consistently exceeded that of secondary schools, reflecting a deep foundation of participation at the primary level.

New Schools, Return Schools, and Total Schools (2013 to 2025)

Year	New Schools	% New	Return Schools	Total Schools
2013	85	100%	0	85
2014	216	80%	55	271
2015	112	65%	60	172
2016	208	80%	53	261
2017	92	52%	85	177
2018	154	43%	202	356
2019	144	39%	221	365

Year	New Schools	% New	Return Schools	Total Schools
2020	142	33%	289	431
2021	78	33%	157	235
2022	91	31%	205	296
2023	105	41%	151	256
2024	353	80%	87	440
2025	202	65%	110	312

Key Observation

In 2025, over 65% of participating schools were new to DEC, demonstrating sustained national growth and the effectiveness of outreach strategies.

Mean Scores by Gender (2013 to 2025)

Year	School Level	Male Mean Score	Female Mean Score
2013	Primary	50.77	51.60
2013	Secondary	49.94	52.51
2014	Primary	44.56	47.27
2014	Secondary	49.34	50.24
2015	Primary	37.97	40.28
2015	Secondary	59.60	60.07
2016	Primary	34.13	35.60
2016	Secondary	51.27	53.29
2017	Primary	35.23	36.16
2017	Secondary	50.14	53.49
2018	Primary	38.00	40.16
2018	Secondary	45.12	46.49
2019	Primary	40.34	42.12
2019	Secondary	43.23	45.23
2020	Primary	44.37	45.33

Year	School Level	Male Mean Score	Female Mean Score
2020	Secondary	46.38	48.43
2021	Primary	39.44	40.03
2021	Secondary	42.32	45.45
2022	Primary	40.33	46.06
2022	Secondary	45.23	48.67
2023	Primary	33.42	35.33
2023	Secondary	44.92	45.67
2024	Primary	27.32	28.70
2024	Secondary	30.73	30.94
2025	Primary	37.61	39.25
2025	Secondary	39.26	40.71

Key Observation

Since 2013, female students have consistently achieved higher mean scores than male students. In 2025, mean scores improved noticeably compared with 2024 for both genders, though both groups remain below 40%.

Figure 5: Mean scores by gender 2013-2025. Female students have consistently outperformed male students; both groups dipped sharply in 2024 before recovering in 2025.

Finalists and Winners

Finalists by Gender (2013 to 2025)

Year	Male	Female	Total
2013	7	22	29
2014	12	17	29
2015	17	43	60
2016	24	36	60
2017	22	48	70
2018	28	49	77
2019	33	44	77
2020	22	33	55
2021	32	40	72
2022	42	67	109
2023	38	76	114
2024	51	66	117
2025	39	62	101

Key Observation

Female finalists have consistently outnumbered male finalists since 2013. In 2025, 61% of all finalists were female students.

Counties with Multiple Finalists in 2025

County	Finalists	County	Finalists
Kiambu	14	Siaya	3
Nairobi	13	Trans Nzoia	3
Bungoma	9	Vihiga	3
Kakamega	9	Kisii	2
Kisumu	8	Machakos	2
Bomet	4	Mandera	2

County	Finalists	County	Finalists
Embu	4	Meru	2
Kajiado	4	Turkana	2
Homa Bay	2	Uasin Gishu	2

Key Observation

Kiambu County produced the highest number of finalists in 2025, accounting for 13.9% of all finalists.

Winners by Gender (2013 to 2025)

Year	Male	Female	Total
2013	2	4	6
2014	6	8	14
2015	4	12	16
2016	10	12	22
2017	10	18	28
2018	21	23	44
2019	20	26	46
2020	16	28	44
2021	26	30	56
2022	21	40	61
2023	30	32	62
2024	32	37	69
2025	36	45	81

Key Observation

The total number of winners grew from 69 in 2024 to 81 in 2025. Female winners accounted for 55.5% (45 out of 81), maintaining a consistent pattern across years.

Figure 6: Winners by gender 2013-2025. The total number of winners has grown from 6 in the inaugural year to 81 in 2025, with female winners consistently outnumbering male winners.

Counties with Highest Number of Winners 2025

County	Winners	County	Winners
Kiambu	17	Nakuru	1
Nairobi	14	Nyeri	1
Bungoma	8	Tana River	1
Siaya	6	Tharaka-Nithi	1
Mandera	2	Trans Nzoia	1
Wajir	2	Turkana	1
Bomet	1	Uasin Gishu	1
Garissa	1	Vihiga	1
Homa Bay	1	Migori	1
Kisii	1	Murang'a	1

Key Observation

Kiambu County produced the highest number of winners in 2025, accounting for over 20% of the total, the sixth consecutive year Kiambu has led the competition in winners.

Awards

All 101 finalists in 2025, including finalists from special needs and art categories, submitted outstanding work according to the judging criteria. Finalists received awards and Finalist certificates, while winners received scholarship funds, uniform support, and computing devices across all categories.

Awards Summary

74 Total Winners	101 Total Finalists	52 Students Receiving Scholarship Funds	All Participating Schools & Teachers Certified
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Prize Structure

- 1st Prize (English & Kiswahili - Primary, Secondary, and Special Needs): KES 40,000 scholarship + KES 10,000 uniform = KES 50,000 per winner.
- 2nd Prize: KES 20,000 scholarship + KES 5,000 uniform = KES 25,000 per winner.
- 3rd Prize: KES 10,000 uniform per winner.
- 20 computing devices for winners in the Special Needs category.
- 6 computing devices each for top students in Primary (English & Kiswahili) and Secondary School categories.
- 2 computing devices for top students in Art, French, German, and Arabic categories.

Awards Breakdown by Category 2025

The tables below summarise winners, finalists, and scholarship funds by school level and category, presented in two parts: first for learners without disabilities, then for learners with disabilities.

Learners Without Disabilities

School Level	Category	Winners	Finalists	Scholarship Funds
Primary	English	6	17	3
Primary	Kiswahili	6	18	3
Primary	French	2	1	2
Primary	Art	2	3	2
Primary	KSL	0	0	0

School Level	Category	Winners	Finalists	Scholarship Funds
Primary	German	1	3	1
Primary	Arabic	2	2	2
Secondary	English	6	16	3
Secondary	Kiswahili	6	19	3
Secondary	French	2	1	2
Secondary	Art	2	3	2
Secondary	KSL	0	0	0
Secondary	German	1	2	2
Secondary	Arabic	2	3	2
Secondary	Mandarin	1	3	1
TOTAL		39	91	28

Learners With Disabilities

School Level	Category	Winners	Finalists	Scholarship Funds
Primary	English	6	0	2
Primary	Kiswahili	5	5	2
Primary	French	0	1	0
Primary	Art	4	5	3
Primary	KSL	3	3	4
Primary	German	0	0	0
Primary	Arabic	0	0	0
Secondary	English	5	4	2
Secondary	Kiswahili	3	4	2
Secondary	French	0	0	1
Secondary	Art	4	4	3
Secondary	KSL	3	3	4
Secondary	German	1	0	0

School Level	Category	Winners	Finalists	Scholarship Funds
Secondary	Arabic	1	1	1
Secondary	Mandarin	0	0	0
TOTAL		35	30	24

Special Needs Students' Participation

In line with eKitabu's mission to achieve transformative and inclusive educational outcomes, the 2025 DEC actively invited Special Needs Schools across Kenya to participate, including learners from the Kakuma refugee camp. The 2025 competition recorded the highest-ever participation of learners with disabilities in DEC history, enabled through close collaboration with the DSNE, eKitabu partners, head teachers, and specialist judges.

452 Total Submissions	43 Special Needs Schools	17 Counties	236 Braille Entries (Record High)
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Special Needs Participation 2024 vs 2025

Category	Counties 2024	Counties 2025	Schools 2024	Schools 2025	Entries 2024	Entries 2025
Primary School	9	11	13	25	175	310
Secondary School	11	6	14	18	66	142
TOTAL	20	17	27	43	241	452

Notable Achievement

2025 registered the highest number of Braille submissions (236) and KSL video entries (78) in DEC history, demonstrating substantial progress in inclusive participation.

Special Needs Participation — 2024 vs 2025

Figure 7: Special Needs participation expanded substantially in 2025 - schools nearly doubled (27 → 43) and entries grew by 88% (241 → 452).

Participation from Kakuma Refugee Camp

Camp	Schools	Total Entries	Female	Male	Learners w/ Disabilities
Kakuma	5	67	18	49	1

Kakuma Finalists and Winners

Camp	Female Finalists	Male Finalists	Total Finalists	Female Winners	Male Winners	Total Winners
Kakuma	5	3	8	2	2	4

Based on the Kakuma data, 73% of submissions were from male participants and 27% from female participants. This disparity reflects the demographics of learners in the target age groups at the camp, including lower enrolment rates of pre-teen and teenage girls due to cultural and social barriers. Moving forward, eKitabu will prioritise collecting more comprehensive registration information and ensuring greater accuracy of data gathered from participating learners in refugee settings.

DEC 2025: Nairobi County Performance

Over the previous seven years, Nairobi County participation had consistently remained below 2,000 entries annually, despite Nairobi having over 1,600 schools and a large learner population. In 2024, eKitabu implemented a school-to-school campaign strategy with direct engagement of head teachers and teachers. Building on this approach, 2025 recorded strong results.

5,513 Total Essays from Nairobi (2025)	45 Nairobi Schools	35 Primary Schools	10 Secondary Schools
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Nairobi Participation Over Five Years

Year	Primary Schools	Secondary Schools	Total Schools	Primary Entries	Secondary Entries	Total Entries
2019	7	4	11	1,435	50	1,485
2021	5	17	22	25	164	189
2022	15	17	32	1,650	57	1,707
2023	12	9	21	992	69	1,061
2024	38	14	52	5,880	270	6,150
2025	35	10	45	5,364	149	5,513

Key Insight

The school-to-school direct engagement strategy implemented in 2024 proved highly effective, maintaining strong Nairobi participation at over 5,500 entries in 2025. This model will be refined and expanded in 2026.

Figure 8: Nairobi County participation over five years. The 2024 direct-engagement strategy produced a step-change in entries, with the momentum sustained into 2025.

DEC 2025 Research Component

In 2025, the Digital Essay Competition integrated a research component aligned with national education priorities and the goals of Kenya's Competency-Based Education (CBE). Students' essays, themed around "What is your favourite book and why?", provided qualitative insights into learners' reading preferences, motivations for reading, access to books, and the influence of family, peers, and teachers on reading habits.

The preliminary analysis below highlights selected trends related to reading themes, language use, and access to reading materials, with attention to inclusion across gender, location, and disability. A separate, comprehensive research report will be produced to present detailed analysis, interpretation, and recommendations.

Most-Read Books in DEC 2025

Book Title	Number of Readers
Mshale wa Matumaini	519
The Bible	410
Wema Hauzi	290
Bridge Without Rivers	280
Daughters of Nature	194
Strange Happenings	187
The Last Laugh	173
The Hidden Package	141
Bembea ya Maisha	130
CRE Book	124
Tears of Joy	122

Figure 9: Most-read books cited by learners in DEC 2025. Mshale wa Matumaini, The Bible, and Wema Hauzi lead, reflecting both classroom and community influences on reading preferences.

How Learners Access Their Favourite Books

Access Channel	Number of Learners
Library	1,555
Purchase	1,355
Borrowed	253
Gift	200
Bookshop	166
Friend	158
School	93
Online	58
Storybook	53
Class Reader	42

Figure 10: How learners access their favourite books. Libraries and direct purchase dominate, while online access and class-reader provision remain comparatively small channels.

Key Research Findings

The initial findings indicate that learners' reading preferences are strongly shaped by access, exposure, and guidance within their immediate learning environments. Books studied or promoted in classrooms, places of worship, and other structured settings are frequently cited as favourites, suggesting that availability and intentional selection play significant roles in shaping reading choices. This highlights the importance of strengthening access to diverse, age-appropriate, and culturally relevant reading materials within schools and community spaces.

The data further suggests that learners value books that go beyond entertainment to offer moral guidance, inspire personal growth, and encourage critical engagement with societal issues. These insights reinforce the role of reading as a tool for values, education and holistic learner development, and underscore the need for continued investment in reading-culture initiatives, teacher support, and inclusive access to quality literature aligned with Competency-Based Education.

DEC 2025: Voices from Our Winners

The voices below, drawn from Kenya's diverse schools and communities, reflect the depth of engagement DEC 2025 inspired among young writers across the country.

"The Big Picture, my favourite book, encouraged me to do my best and reach higher for my dreams. It truly taught me that intelligence and vision is necessary for shaping my character."

Female, DEC 2025 Winner - Secondary School English Category, Limuru Girls High School, Kiambu County

"Kila msomaji na mpenzi na ashiki wa lugha ya Kiswahili hawezi kujizuia kukipenda kitabu hiki. Ukweli na usemwe, chanda chema na kivishwe pete. Iwapo hujakisoma kitabu hiki, Kidagaa Kimemwozea, basi kidagaa kimekuoza kwa kuwa haujajua uhondo unaoukosa."

Male, DEC 2025 Winner - Secondary School Kiswahili Category, Chogoria Boys High School, Tharaka-Nithi County

"Fathers of Nations is unlike any other book I have read. On the surface, it is a mystery story full of suspense and confusion, but if you read it carefully you realise that each character represents a part of Africa."

Male, DEC 2025 Winner - Secondary School English Category, Njiiri School, Murang'a County

DEC 2025: Highlights and Observations

The 2025 Digital Essay Competition delivered strong results across participation, inclusivity, innovation, and research: advancing eKitabu’s mission and reinforcing the programme’s role as a leading national platform for learner expression.

- DEC 2025 generated 15,221 entries across all categories from 312 schools in 35 counties.
- 202 schools (65% of the total) were participating in DEC for the first time, demonstrating sustained national growth and the effectiveness of outreach strategies.
- Inclusivity was a defining feature of DEC 2025. The competition recorded the highest-ever participation of learners with disabilities, 452 submissions from 43 special needs schools across 17 counties, with strong growth in Braille and Kenyan Sign Language categories.
- DEC 2025 marked a significant programmatic shift through the introduction of a structured research component linked to the essay theme, “What is your favourite book and why?”, directly aligning the Competition with Competency-Based Education (CBE).
- 67 entries were received from Kakuma refugee camp, including submissions from learners with disabilities.
- DEC 2025 strengthened quality and efficiency through the adoption of online second-round judging.
- Language categories expanded with the introduction of Mandarin, alongside the new Chapa Shairi poetry category.
- Girls continued to outperform boys in participation, finalist representation, and winners, accounting for over 55% of national winners (45 out of 81), reinforcing long-standing gender trends in literacy engagement.
- Kiambu County produced the highest number of winners for the sixth consecutive year, with over 20% of the total winners.

Strategies for Impact and Growth

What Has Worked Over the Years

1. Seek programme approval from the Ministry of Education on time.
2. Involve more stakeholders, teachers, partners, and agents in developing DEC questions.
3. Focus on maximising the number of schools to extend county reach and student participation.
4. Thorough advance planning: the DEC is a year-round cycle requiring consistent coordination.
5. Recruit more agents, focusing on counties with low or no representation.
6. Raise awareness among special needs schools early and ensure learners with different disabilities participate.
7. Secure prizes on time to incentivise participation.
8. Ensure all DEC teachers receive qualitative and quantitative written feedback.
9. Work with teachers to ensure complete and accurate registration and submission of data.
10. Use multi-channel communication: calls, posters, emails, WhatsApp, and bulk SMS.
11. Conduct Regional Kick-Off (RKO) events to target repeat schools and re-engage communities.
12. Attract sponsors for different categories (e.g. French, German, Art) to increase exposure.
13. Continue to assess the quantitative impact of DEC on schools and students.
14. Strengthen partnerships with ICT champions and teachers in schools.

Observations and Lessons Learnt in 2025

1. The inclusion of a research component proved to be a valuable addition, strengthening evidence-based learning and informing future planning.
2. Plagiarism and AI-generated content detection measures need further strengthening in 2026.
3. Better data-collection tools are needed for learners submitting hard-copy essays.
4. There is potential for a mentorship pathway to support top student authors toward publishing their work.
5. Online second-round judging was highly effective, significantly reducing turnaround time while maintaining quality.
6. Identifying like-minded partners to improve awards and expand DEC reach remains a priority.
7. Automated, personalised feedback to enhance students' writing and learning would add significant value.

Looking Ahead: DEC 2026

The 2026 Digital Essay Competition is planned to launch on 5th March 2026, with the submission period open through 31st July 2026, closing on 7th August 2026. Winners will be announced at the Prize-Giving Ceremony on 25th September 2026.

Students will register and submit their essays through essay.ekitabu.com or submit physical copies to eKitabu's office through agents or by courier.

DEC 2026 Key Dates

Launch: 5th March 2026 | Submission Closes: 7th August 2026 | Prize-Giving: 25th September 2026

The Digital Essay Competition gives students in Kenya the chance to contribute their voices and visions to issues affecting them and their communities, helping them develop critical thinking and innovative minds.

Acknowledgements

eKitabu thanks the Ministry of Education for its ongoing support of the Digital Essay Competition and looks forward to deepened collaboration in 2026.

We extend our sincere appreciation to the DEC 2025 sponsors for supporting this cause: Ubongo International, Kenya Publishers Association (KPA), Kenya Primary School Heads Association (KEPSHA), Kenya Secondary School Heads Association (KESSHA), and Kenya Private Schools Association (KPSA).

We thank our first and second round judges and the Kenya Institute for the Blind (KIB) judges for their invaluable contributions to the programme. Thanks also to the DEC 2025 field agents, and to all head teachers and teachers who championed the programme in 2025.

Finally, we thank the entire eKitabu team for the planning, dedication, and teamwork in executing DEC 2025.

Tuko Digital!

Annex: DEC 2025 Photos and Feedback Forms

Figure 11: Digital Essay Competition 2025 launch in May at Kapsabet High School in Nandi County

Figure 12: DEC 2025 winner, accompanied by her teacher during the awards ceremony at the Nairobi International Book Fair (NIBF) in Nairobi County

A Scout march by State House Primary School learners during the DEC 2025 Primary School launch at the school in Nairobi County.

DEC 2025 school awarding at Moi Avenue Primary and JS School in Nairobi County.

DEC 2025 Kenyan Sign Language Judges at the eKitabu office in Nairobi during the judging of the essays.

Some of the DEC 2025 winners accompanied by their teacher at the Nairobi International Book Fair (NIBF) in Nairobi County.

Student Details Form

Field	Details
Name of Student	
Class / Form	
Essay ID	
Name of School	
County	

Essay Scoring Sheet

Criterion	Description	Points (1–20)
a. Comprehension	How well does the essay address the question?	
b. Organisation	Logical progression and supporting evidence	
c. Conclusions	Logical and compelling conclusions	
d. Creativity	Innovative or creative angle on the topic	
e. Writing	Grammar, spelling, punctuation, conciseness	
TOTAL		/ 100

<p>Grading Bands 80–100: A 70–79: B 60–69: C 50–59: D Below 50: Fail</p>
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DEC Judges' Comments for the Student

Comments	Way Forward

School Feedback Form

Field	Details
Name of School	
Head Teacher / Contact Teacher	
County	
Number of DEC Entries	

Contact Information

Headquarters — Kenya	USA Office	Report Contact
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